

Polarographic Study of the Composition and Formation Constants of Bromide Complexes of Pb(II)

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The polarographic reduction of Pb(II) in bromide solution is a reversible and diffusion controlled process. The $E_{1/2}$ shifts towards more negative value with the increase of bromide ion concentration, indicating the complex formation. The composition and formation constants have been calculated by De Ford and Hume's method at a constant ionic strength ($\mu=1.0$). Presence of three complex species: $PbBr^+$, $PbBr_2$ and $PbBr_3^-$ has been indicated. The overall formation constants at 25° have been found to be 1.0, 2.0 and 17.2 respectively. The percentage distribution of Pb(II) in various forms as a function of bromide ion concentration has been presented.

THOUGH, the polarographic behaviour of Pb(II) in complexing and non-complexing supporting electrolytes has been studied by a number of workers¹⁻⁷, yet a polarographic study of its bromide complexes is lacking. The present communication deals with the determination of the composition and formation constants of bromide complexes of Pb(II) using De Ford and Hume's method⁸.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R., B.D.H. grade. The solution of Pb(II) was prepared by dissolving a weighed amount of $Pb(NO_3)_2$ in conductivity water. KNO_3 was used to keep a constant ionic strength since with $NaClO_4$ precipitation occurred. KBr was used as a complexing agent.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal, CLO2) in conjunction with Toshniwal polyflex galvanometer (PL 50) was used. All the measurements were done at 25°

0.1°. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used as a maximum suppressor. Purified hydrogen was passed through the solutions for removing dissolved oxygen. Saturated

calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode.

The d.m.e had the following characteristics :

$$m = 3.60 \text{ mg sec}^{-1}$$

$$t = 2.10 \text{ sec. (open circuit, in } 0.1 \text{ M } KNO_3)$$

$$m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.66 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$$

$$h_{\text{corr.}} = 30.2 \text{ cm.}$$

Results and Discussion

In each case, a single well defined reduction wave appeared. The plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ and i_d vs conc. of Pb(II) were found to be linear, indicating that the reduction is diffusion-controlled. The plots of $\log \frac{i}{i_a - i}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$ were found to be linear with a slope of the order of 31 ± 2 mV, showing the reversibility of the reduction. The value of 'n' was found to be 2. The $E_{1/2}$ was found to shift towards more negative values with increasing bromide concentration, showing the formation of the complexes between Pb(II) and bromide ion.

TABLE I

Concentration of $Pb^{2+} = 1 \times 10^{-3} M$.

Analysis of $E_{1/2}$ of lead in bromide medium with $\mu = 1.0$

KBr M	$E_{1/2} (-V)$	i_d division	Slope (mV)	$F_0 [X]$	$F_1 [X]$	$F_2 [X]$	$F_3 [X]$
0.0	0.390	160	32	—	—	—	—
0.2	0.394	173	32	1.26	1.32	—	—
0.3	0.397	172	32	1.48	1.61	2.05	—
0.4	0.404	170	32	2.55	3.87	7.14	12.81
0.5	0.409	172	32	4.08	6.17	10.34	16.67
0.6	0.415	172	32	6.52	9.20	13.66	19.44
0.7	0.419	174	34	8.80	11.14	14.50	17.83
0.8	0.423	176	34	11.88	13.60	15.75	17.20
0.9	0.426	180	34	15.84	16.50	17.21	16.90
1.0	0.430	170	34	21.20	20.20	19.20	17.20

A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ (C_x = bromide ion concentration in M) is found to be a smooth curve instead of a straight line (Fig. 1), which shows the presence of two or more complexes. The classical method due to

Fig. 1 : Plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $-\log C_x$ for Lead-Bromide system.

Lingane⁹ could not be applied for the calculation of the composition and formation constants of the complexes. For this purpose De Ford and Hume's method¹⁰ has been used. This method consists of graphical differentiation of the $F_0[X]$ term which can be obtained from polarographic data :

$$F_0[X] = \text{antilog} \left[\frac{n}{0.0591} \left\{ (E_{1/2})_s - (E_{1/2})_c \right\} + \log \frac{I_s}{I_0} \right] \quad (1)$$

at 25° , where 'n' is the number of electrons involved in the reduction process, $E_{1/2}$ refers to the half-wave potential. I is diffusion current constant and the subscripts 's' and 'c' refer to the simple (aquo) ion and the same ion in complexing media, respectively. In solutions with excess ligand present and a constant ionic strength, it is known that

$$F_0[X] = 1 + \beta_1[X] + \beta_2[X]^2 + \beta_3[X]^3 + \dots \quad (2)$$

$$F_1[X] = \left\{ \frac{F_0[X] - 1}{[X]} \right\} = \beta_1 + \beta_2[X] + \dots \quad (3)$$

$$F_2[X] = \left\{ \frac{F_1[X] - \beta_1}{[X]} \right\} = \beta_2 + \beta_3[X] + \dots \quad (4)$$

$$F_3[X] = \left\{ \frac{F_2[X] - \beta_2}{[X]} \right\} = \beta_3 + \beta_4[X] + \dots \quad (5)$$

$$\beta_1 = 1.0, \beta_2 = 2.0, \beta_3 = 17.2$$

where $\beta_1, \beta_2, \dots$ are the different overall formation constants and $[X]$ is the equilibrium concentration of the ligand (which closely approximates the analytical concentration when an excess is present).

The experimentally determined values of half wave potentials together with $F_j[X]$ values calculated from equations (1) to (5) are recorded in Table 1. The overall formation constants were obtained by a graphical extrapolation of the $F_j[X]$ functions to the zero ligand concentration (Fig. 2). The overall formation constants for the three complex species; $PbBr^+$, $PbBr_2$ and $PbBr_3^-$ at 25° come out to be 1.0, 2.0 and 17.2 respectively ($\mu=1.0$).

Fig. 2 : $F_j(X)$ plots for Lead-Bromide system.

The percentage distribution of $Pb(II)$ in its various forms as a function of the free bromide ion concentration has been presented in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3 : Percentage distribution of Lead in various forms as a function of bromide ion concentration.

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